

Nanomaterials : A new dimension in material science^ψ

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Nanoscience is one of the most flourishing interdisciplinary fields in the last two decades where chemists, material scientists, biochemists, physicists and engineers are cooperatively involved to harness the academic and application potentials of the field. It attempts to prepare and organize objects within tiny length-scale, and to understand the evolution of bulk properties from the molecular properties. It has been observed that the band gap, which is an important property of semiconductors, can be varied with changing particle size in the nano-length scale. For example, the band gap in CdS nanoparticles can be varied over a wide range from 5–2.5 eV for size variation from molecular dimension to macroscopic crystal. Further, the radiative lifetime for the lowest allowed optical excitation ranges from tens of pico-seconds to several nanoseconds¹, and the energy above the band gap required to add an excess charge decreases by 0.5 eV², and the melting temperature of the material increases from 400 to 1600 °C³, while the pressure required to induce transformation from a four to a six-coordinated phase decreases from 9 to 2 GPa⁴.

The products in a chemical reaction, if insoluble in the solvent, come closer and coalesce to minimize surface free energy and hence the surface area⁵⁻⁷. Sometimes they are crystalline and sometimes amorphous. Its crystallinity depends on the nature of the material viz. the lattice energy, the solvation energy, reaction condition, etc. A chemical reaction is involved with rearrangements in the energy levels of the components and hence in the atomic orbitals. In the product, a new set of orbitals are formed and the valence shell electrons manifest its physicochemical properties. Spectroscopically, the band gap is the energy difference between the HOMO and LUMO.

On increasing crystal growth, the individual molecular HOMO's interact (overlap) among themselves to form a band structure called the valence band⁸ wherein the energy of the resultant crystal HOMO becomes fuzzy. Similarly, the individual molecular LUMO's combine among themselves to lead to the formation of the resultant conduction band. The energy difference between the valence band and the conduction band is considered as the band gap of the crystal⁹. During crystal growth, the number of superimposing molecular energy levels in either bands increases, which in turn, increases the overlap among the individual energy levels, and correspondingly the band gap of the crystal decreases. Thus, the band gap of a material can be tuned by controlling its crystal size. Semiconductors have moderate band gap which increases with decreasing particle size. The size dependant band gap in the nanomaterials may lead to newer electrical and optical properties having prospects for extensive practical uses.

It is known that restriction of particle size to lower value increases the surface area to volume ratio. This enhances its efficiency in catalysis, especially the free radical reactions¹⁰. Metallic Au, Ag, Cu nanomaterials are easily recognized from their characteristic surface plasmon resonance bands in the absorption spectrum at 520¹¹, 380¹²⁻¹⁴ and 580 nm¹⁵ respectively. This phenomenon arises in the presence of conduction band intersected by the Fermi level, which enables electron-hole pairs of all energies to be excited⁹. This is a dipolar excitation of the entire particle between the negatively charged free electron-gas in the nanocrystal and its positively charged core¹⁶. The energy of this transition depends on the free-electron density and the surrounding

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dielectric medium (as a result of exchange interaction). The free radical generated by photoirradiation or γ -illumination can diffuse to a metallic colloidal particle in solution, increasing the Fermi level in the metal to a more negative potential by way of transferring electrons to them¹⁰. This makes the microelectrode like usage of metal nanoparticles feasible. One colloidal particle can take up several electrons, which can be used up in efficient reduction of the substrate, and hence the catalytic efficacy is increased. Since the surface structure is in general, a defect structure¹⁷, decreasing crystal size increases the relative amount of defect structure, which significantly affects the electrical, photophysical and optical properties of the crystal, and leads to nonlinear properties.

Substantial variation of electrical and optical properties on reducing particle size is expected for materials having thermal energy (kT) smaller than the spacing in energy levels¹⁸. Otherwise, the thermal energy itself promotes the HOMO to the LUMO. In semiconductors, for a given temperature, this transition occurs at a relatively large size compared to metal, insulator and molecular crystals (van der Waals crystal). This difference is due to accumulation of the bands of a solid about the atomic energy levels, with the width of the band related to strength of the nearest-neighbour interactions. For molecular crystals, the nearest neighbour interactions are weak, the bands are very narrow, and consequently not much size-tunable optical and electrical properties are expected in the nanocrystal regime. As the cluster size increases, the center of a band is developed first and the edge last¹⁸. In metals, where the Fermi level lies at the center of a band and the relevant energy level spacing is small, at temperatures above a few K, the electrical and optical properties resemble those of continuum, even at relatively smaller size^{19,20}. In semiconductors, however, the Fermi level lies between two bands, such that the band edges dominate the low energy optical and electrical behaviour¹⁸.

Quantum confinement :

On exposure to light of appropriate frequencies, the valence band electron is excited to the conduction band and becomes labile. A vacancy, called the hole, is correspondingly generated in the valence band. The defect surface structures can act as effective site for the photogenerated electron and holes, or for the electron-hole pair (known as the exciton). The defect surface structures can thus impart some interesting photophysical properties to the nanocrystallites.

The photogenerated labile electron is subjected to move

freely within the confined crystal regime and this problem is similar to the quantum mechanical problem of a particle restricted within an infinite spherical potential well²¹⁻²³ considering the quantized electronic states having maximum probability density inside the nanocrystal (Fig. 1), with a node on the surface²⁴.

Fig. 1. Potential well formed in any one dimension (x, y or z) in the conduction and the valence bands. The energy levels of the excited carriers (electrons and holes) become quantized due to the finite size of the semiconductor.

Theoretically, the electron-hole pair (forming the first excited state) can be treated using the effective mass approximation²⁵ which assumes parabolic conduction and valence bands with bulk effective masses for the electron and the hole¹⁶ as shown in Figs. 2A and 2B. Such a particle (the electron-hole pair) in a spherical well (the most probable shape is spherical) with radius $r = a$, under restrictions of potential energy $V(r) = 0$ for $r < a$ and $V(r) = \infty$ for $r > a$ is given by the wave function²⁶

$$\varphi_{n,l,m}(\rho, \theta, \phi) = (C/r) j_l(k_{n,l} r) Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) \quad (1)$$

where C is the normalization constant, Y_l^m is a spherical harmonic and $j_l(k_{n,l} r)$ is the l -th order spherical Bessel function, and $k_{n,l} = \alpha_{n,l}/a$, with $\alpha_{n,l}$ the n -th zero of l . Due to symmetry reason, the wave functions are similar to the atomic like orbitals, the energies are similar to the kinetic energy of the free particle superimposed by the quantization of the wave vector $k_{n,l}$ by the spherical boundary condition. Energy of the particle is given by the relation,

$$E_{n,l} = \hbar^2 \alpha_{n,l}^2 / 8\pi^2 m_0 a^2 \quad (2)$$

where m_0 is the rest mass of the electron-hole pair. The length scale of the photogenerated electron-hole pair is given by the Bohr radius, characteristic for the individual material and is given by¹⁷

Fig. 2. (A) Simple two-band model for direct gap semiconductors. The real band structure (solid line) is approximated by parabolic bands (dashed line) in effective mass approximation. The curvature of bands reflects effective mass of electron in conduction band and that of hole in valence band. (B) Optical transitions in finite size semiconductor QD's are discrete due to the quantization of the bulk band diagram. An electron is promoted into the conduction band creating a hole in the valence band.

$$a_B = (h^2\epsilon / 4\pi^2e^2m^*) \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is the bulk dielectric constant of the material, h is the Planck constant and m^* is the effective mass of the hole-electron pair, given by the relation,

$$1/m^* = 0.5(1/m_e + 1/m_h) \quad (4)$$

with m_e and m_h being the electron and hole effective masses in the bulk material.

Thus, on decreasing particle size, the photogenerated electron becomes more and more restricted in space and its energy increases in terms of eq. (2). As a consequence, the oscillator strength²⁷ is accumulated in a few transitions only leading to the optical nonlinear property. This, in turn, drastically changes the density of electronic states, which can be anticipated by considering the position-momentum relation in free space¹⁸. For a free particle or a particle under a periodic potential in a crystal lattice, both energy and momentum can be determined precisely whereas the position remains totally uncertain. For a localized particle, the energy can still be well defined, but the decreased uncertainty in position introduces some uncertainty in momentum in terms of Heisenberg uncertainty principle. The discrete energy states of the particle, in that case, can be viewed as a superposition of bulk eigenstates in momentum space²⁶. From the known energy-momentum relation, one can now find a series of transitions occurring at slightly decreased energy in the

bulk phase compensated by a single and intense transition in nanoparticles. This is the so-called optical enhancement effect²⁸. The optical enhancement effect can also be viewed in another way. On decreasing particle size, the density of state (which for bulk material is a continually variable function of energy) behaves as a collection of discrete states^{29,30} (the density of states varies as delta function of energy variable in ideal case²⁸) as shown in Fig. 3. So the number of possible transitions decreases. To maintain the constancy of the integrated area as that in the bulk material (as a consequence to maintain the 1 : 1 ratio between the number of photon absorbed and the number of transition occurring) the height of the peak must increase. i.e. the number of transitions at that particular energy must increase. This obviously increases the optical density (proportional to the number of transitions) at the particular wavelength, which is the optical enhancement effect. The spacing between the discrete levels, δ , is given by, $4E_F/3N$, where E_F is the Fermi energy of the metal³¹, and N is the Avogadro number.

The problem can also be visualized as a perturbation

Fig. 3. Density of electronic states in (A) bulk, (B) ideal QD and (C) real QD. The optical absorption spectrum is roughly proportional to the density of states.

problem, where crystal growth restriction acts as the perturbation on the bulk band gap (the energy difference between HOMO and LUMO in the bulk material, E_G) and lead to unwinding of the band structure in the valence and conduction shell of the bulk material. The perturbation acts as the confinement energy (E_C) on the bulk band gap (E_G), and the energy of the size-quantized material (E_g) is given as

$$E_g = E_G + E_C \quad (5)$$

where E_g is the band gap of the size quantized material.

Dielectric confinement :

Another important confinement effect arises out of the presence of interface between the cluster and the surrounding medium that is especially important for nanomaterials because of the large surface area to vol-

ume ratio in them¹⁷. The clusters are, in general, surrounded by dielectrics, e.g. air, organic solvents, polymers, glass etc., with lower refractive index compared to the inorganic nano materials. This refractive index boundary induces an enhancement of the field intensity near, at or inside the clusters compared to the incident intensity. This enhancement in local field intensity is called the dielectric confinement and considerably affects the photophysical properties.

Nonlinear optical property :

Normally, the optical properties of a material do not depend on the intensity of light. At high-enough intensities, materials become nonlinear, i.e. the light changes the properties of the material, which can be sensed by another "probe" light beam or by the beam that changes the material itself²⁸. The first step in the field of optical non-linearity was evidenced long back in early 60's when the observation of second harmonic generation in quartz crystal was proposed³². The third-order optical nonlinearity can simply be explained if only one laser frequency is used in the optical process. A material possesses third order optical nonlinearity if its refractive index (n) depends on the intensity of the incident light (I) reversibly, i.e.

$$n = n_0 + n_2 I \quad (6)$$

where n_0 is the refractive index at low-intensity limit and n_2 is called the second nonlinear refraction coefficient. Under such a condition, the induced polarization of the material has a cubic dependence on the electric field of the incident light³³, hence the term third-order nonlinear effect is used. Such a change in the refractive index can be induced by either a resonant or a nonresonant process. For a resonant process, the frequency of the incident light overlaps with an electronic absorption band, by either a one-photon or a multiphoton process. The absorption of energy generates an excited state population, which, in turn, induces a transient change in the absorption spectrum of the material due to the bleaching of the ground state absorption and/or the appearance of the excited state absorption. This change in the absorption coefficient, α , gives rise to a change in the refractive index, since they are interdependent according to the Kramers-Kronig relations³⁴. A nonlinear optical coefficient α_2 can be defined similarly to eq. (6),

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 + \alpha_2 I \quad (7)$$

where α_0 is the absorption coefficient at the low intensity limit. The phenomenon is generally monitored by flash photolysis (pump-probe technique): where a short pulse

of laser is used to excite the material and a second pulse (or lamp) is used to probe the change in the absorption spectrum.

For a nonresonant process, light is not absorbed by the sample. The optical nonlinearity basically originates from the anharmonicity of the electronic system. The nonresonant optical nonlinearity of a material is described via the perturbational approach. The polarization P_d induced in a medium by an external electromagnetic field, E , can be written as

$$P_d = \chi^{(1)}E + \chi^{(2)}EE + \chi^{(3)}EEE + \dots \quad (8)$$

where $\chi^{(n)}$ is n 'th order susceptibility. The third order susceptibility, $\chi^{(3)}$, describes the third harmonic generation, four wave mixing, and the optical Kerr effect³⁵. Optical switching³³ and image processing³⁶ are important fields of application of $\chi^{(3)}$ process. Optical switches are potentially much faster than electrical switches.

Spectroscopic properties :

Nanocrystals act like molecules as they interact with light via their electronic transition dipole³⁷. The unwinding of the band structure in the valence and conduction band structure of semiconductor nanocrystals, a result of the quantum confinement effect, leads to an increase in the electronic transition energy and hence a blue shift in the absorption maximum. Moreover, the discreteness imposed by the spatial restriction on the band structure leads to high-energy specific transitions among the electronic states at the expense of reduced absorption at other energies²⁸. The increased density of states at a particular electronic energy level (i.e. accumulation of oscillator strength into just a few transitions) leads to an enhancement in the absorption at aforespecific energy eigenstates, leading to optical enhancement effect.

The photogeneration of the electron in the conduction band automatically creates a hole or vacancy in the valence band, and the hole and the photogenerated labile electron can combine as a result of electrostatic attraction, exchange forces and lattice vibration leading to an electron-hole pair, called the exciton, which can also be considered as the first electronically excited state. In many molecules vibronic interaction in the excited state is strong as the wave function is localized on just one or a few bonds³⁷. The molecular excited state has a different structure, which promotes fast nonradiative deactivation into the ground state. Emission quantum yields can be low, and often sensitive to quenching by the local environment. In large nanocrystal assemblies, there are plenty of electron-hole pairs, and the excitons are not being bound

with respect to the thermal energy kT , at room temperature²⁴, they dissociate in larger crystals. Carrier recombination is then a many-body collision problem as in the bulk. In nanocrystal, there is only a single electron-hole pair, which cannot disintegrate as it is bound by the spatial restriction within the crystal. As a result, the rate of radiationless internal conversion, which is a unimolecular decay of the electronic energy into heat, is extremely slow. Excited state thus finds relatively smaller number of channels to decay to the ground state in a defect-free semiconductor nanocrystal leading to enhanced luminescence efficiency. It is, therefore, legitimate to say that the increased luminescence efficiency on size quantized nanocrystal is not due to increase in the rate of radiative decay but it is governed mostly by decrease in the rate of non-radiative decay processes²⁴. In a 2.3 nm CdSe nanocrystal, the wave function is delocalised over ~ 100 unit cells with little probability density at the surface in contrast to a single molecule described earlier³⁷. So, in the absence of internal or surface defects, a nanocrystal should exhibit near unity fluorescence quantum yield, and partial protection from quenching. The emission spectrum is expected to be a sharp one due to smaller Franck-Condon factor in nanocrystals.

Due to enhanced surface area to volume ratio in nanocrystals, the fraction of surface atoms in a nanocrystal is greater in comparison to bulk material. This leads to increase in the fraction of unbalanced surface bonds. The defect surface structure predominating in nanocrystals act as trapping sites for the photogenerated electron-hole pair, leading to a decrease in the luminescence quantum yield. Surface passivation is the chemical process by which the unbalanced surface bonds are bonded to another material, generally with much higher band gap and hence eliminates all the energy levels inside the gap¹⁸. Passivated semiconductor nanomaterials, therefore, have a comparatively larger luminescence quantum yield. Semiconductor light emitting diodes have narrow emission bands and can show near 30% efficiency in converting electrical power into light³⁷. Semiconductor lasers and diodes³⁸⁻⁴¹ also show excellent long-term stability against photochemical and current-induced degradation compared to many organic materials.

Electrical property :

For a nanocrystal surrounded by a medium with dielectric constant ϵ , the capacitance of the nanocrystal is given by $C(r) = 4\pi\epsilon_0 r\epsilon$ (ϵ and ϵ_0 being permittivity of the medium and that of vacuum) and the energy required to add a single charge is given by the charging energy,

$E_C = e^2/2C(r)$ ⁴². So addition of a single electron, i.e. reduction of the nanocrystallite costs energy, because a charge carrier is no longer solvated in an effectively infinite medium. This can be viewed in the I - V (current-voltage) plots in cyclic voltametry of the nanocrystal at temperature lower than the charging energy as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. I - V curves showing the effect of finite size on conduction. At low temperature the energy cost to add charge to a NC gives rise to an onset to current flow, Coulomb blockade. The expanded portion shows, for small enough metal NCs, the density of electronic state are quantized. The I - V curve shows steps just above the Coulomb blockade as current arises from tunneling through the discrete energy levels of the NC.

At a potential, above the threshold for carrier tunneling, finer investigation of the high resolution cyclic voltametry leads to fingerprints of discrete energy levels in the nanocrystals (inset, Fig. 4). At lower temperatures, the energy cost to add charge to a nanocrystal gives rise to an onset of current flow called the Coulomb blockade⁴³.

The quantum dot structures are the most sensitive instruments known for the measurement of current and local fields and may be used for that purpose or possibly as switches in future, because the electrons and holes are necessarily delocalized over the entire structure. Analogous structures, in which colloidal nanocrystals of metals and semiconductors are deposited between electrodes, will undoubtedly be investigated extensively in the near future. These structures will be particularly interesting be-

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of self-aggregation of surfactant monolayer, spherical micelle, double layer (lamellar) and elongated vesicle, sometimes-called liposome as formed on increasing surfactant concentration.

cause the energy level spacing attributable to quantum confinement is comparable to or even greater than the charging energy in the crystallites that are substantially smaller than the Bohr radius of the bulk semiconductor exciton. In this regime, tunneling and transport occur through single quantum levels of the dot.

Preparation of nanodispersion :

The main problem in preparing nanometer range particles in solution is their inherent tendency towards coagulation in order to minimize surface free energy. This tendency can be suppressed in a number of ways. The particles can be prepared in rigid or semi rigid matrices like zeolite, glass, membrane and gel templates. The rigidity of the template, in these cases, resists rapid molecular diffusion and hence the tendency of coagulation. In the vapor phase reaction method, the large interparticle separation invalidates the attractive van der Waals' force to operate. Such an advantage lacks in solution phase preparation. Bawendi and his group have mastered the method of capping the nanoparticles for stabilization⁴⁴. The crystallites were organically capped using tri-*n*-octylphosphine (TOP), tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO), trimethylsilyl-chalconides, etc. The most effective temperature required yielding good crystal quality, smaller crystal size and smaller polydispersity in size need to be calibrated in this method. The hydrophobic repulsion force among the caps acts as a potential barrier against the particle coagulation. The nanoparticles prepared in this method are high quality, but the reaction requires harsh/difficult conditions, such as the injection of hazardous metal alkyls at elevated temperatures (~ 350 °C)⁴⁵. Trindade and O'Brien prepared cadmium dithio- and diselenocarbamate complexes as precursors for the preparation of tetraoctylphosphine oxide (TOPO) capped Group II-IV materials^{46,47}. Guyot-Sionnest⁴⁸ and Revaprasadu⁴⁹ simultaneously reported the preparation of TOPO capped ZnSe along the root of Murrey *et al.*⁴⁴. Although TOPO is the only Lewis base to be utilized in the nanocrystallite preparation, the TOPO capped nanoparticles are found to

degrade in the presence of light and oxygen forming unstable chalcogen oxide species that leave surface defects⁵⁰. Thiols found exclusive application in this respect⁵¹⁻⁶⁰.

Due to the amphiphilic nature, surfactants in aqueous solution favourably populate at the air/water interface. On increasing surfactant concentration, the surface population increases gradually and after a threshold concentration, the amphiphiles may form self-assembled entities in order to avoid the water-tail incapability. Such assemblies are termed as micelles⁶¹⁻⁶³, bilayers, vesicles⁶⁴, lamellar phases⁶⁵, etc. as shown in Fig. 5, depending on their structure and morphology. In all these assemblies only the head group of the surfactant molecules are projected towards the aqueous part in the solution while the tail form a nonpolar core region in them.

Surfactants like sodium dodecylsulfate [SDS]^{66,67}, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide [CTAB]^{67,68} and kinked surfactants like oleic acid^{69,70} have been successfully used as capping agents in stabilizing metallic nanoparticles like Au, Cu, Ag, Co, etc. Wei and coworkers^{71,72} extensively used the multidentate surfactant resorcinerane as ligand in the stabilization of Au nanodispersion. We have reported the preparation of PbS nanoparticle in aqueous AOT medium⁷³, where the coordination from the anionic surfactant to the nanodispersion acted as a barrier towards coagulation. We have also reported the preparation and characterization of ZnS⁷⁴ and CoS₂^{75a,b} and CdS/HgS co-colloid and their sandwich⁷⁶ in micellar medium. Surface capping also passivates the surface defects and thereby can significantly improve the electrical and optical properties of nanodispersions.

The preparation of PbS nanomaterial⁷³ was described using 10 mM aqueous solution of the double-tailed surfactant sodium bis(ethyl-2-hexyl)sulphosuccinate (AOT) solution as the template. The particles induced a reversal of the micellar structure and the nano-dispersion is stabilized by capping from the polar head group of AOT. The particle-surfactant aggregates were then stabilized by another layer of surfactant pointing their ionic head-groups toward the aqueous phase. The nanoparticle, thus, induced some vesicle-like structure of the AOT aggregates in aqueous solution. Size of the as prepared nanoparticles were measured using dynamic light scattering (DLS) in solution phase and transmission electron microscopic (in solid phase) techniques. The TEM micrographs are presented in Fig. 6. Spectroscopic studies of the nano-dispersion was performed using UV-Vis and fluorescence techniques and the variation in the absorption and emission maxima and their relative intensities were explained on the basis of the established theories described earlier.

Fig. 6. Transmission electron micrograph of PbS nanoparticle at different concentration, prepared in 23.5 mM aqueous AOT medium (A) $[PbS] = 6.40 \times 10^{-5} M$, (B) $8.40 \times 10^{-5} M$ and (C) $12.18 \times 10^{-5} M$.

The major importance of the ZnS nanoparticle⁷⁴ prepared in aqueous micellar sodium dodecylsulphate (SDS) medium is their triangular shape as evidenced from the transmission electron microscopy (shown in Fig. 7). Absorption and emission spectroscopy were used to characterize the material. We also introduced the as prepared ZnS particles in membrane matrix formed using polyvinyl chloride (PVC). The membrane resulted Nernstian response and could be used as a Zn^{2+} selective membrane electrode, reversible with respect to Zn^{2+} .

Fig. 7. Transmission electron micrograph of ZnS nanoparticles prepared in 10 mM aqueous SDS (A) $[ZnS] = 50 \mu M$, (B) $[ZnS] = 100 \mu M$

The preparation and characterization of CoS_2 ^{75a,b} nanomaterials was described in the micellar medium of the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)^{75a} and anionic surfactants SDS and AOT^{75b}. In the CTAB medium, the acidic pH induced by the micellar medium helps the formation of the disulfide nanoparticle. The nanoparticles were then capped with thiophenol in aqueous and 1 : 1 (v/v) water-ethanol mixture. The capping method was kinetically favoured in the water-ethanol medium. Colour of the capped materials prepared in either medium was different, black in water

medium and violet in water-ethanol medium. The absorption spectrum of the black particles differed from that of the uncapped particles, probably as a result of the interaction of the Co-core with the phenyl ring of the thiophenolate group. The violet colour of the particles prepared in the water-ethanol medium was due to the ethanol induced free-radical generation, which assisted in the charge transfer colour. Electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy (ESIMS) was used to gather idea about composition of the capped particles. X-Ray diffraction studies confirmed the pyrite structure of the materials. The TEM micrographs of the capped and uncapped particles prepared in CTAB medium under different drying conditions are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. TEM micrograph of the CoS_2 particle prepared in 10 mM aqueous CTAB medium. Conditions: Uncapped particle, (A) vacuum dried, (B) dried by evaporation. Thiophenol capped particles (C) dried in vacuum, (D) dried by evaporation. The size distribution of the particles in Fig. 5C has been shown in inset using Gaussian fitting.

The CoS_2 nanoparticles prepared in aqueous AOT medium evidenced agglomerated spherical particles in the network offered by the surfactant medium and is shown in Fig. 9, whereas those prepared in the aqueous SDS medium evidenced well-separated nearly spherical particles (Fig. 10). The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns with five spherical patterns evidenced crystallinity of the particles as shown in Fig. 11. The better crystallization of the particles in SDS medium was also evidenced from the sharpness of the particles prepared in the medium. We have also studied the core-shell and composites of HgS-CdS nanomaterials in micellar medium of CTAB. The TEM micrograms are presented in Fig. 12.

Fig. 9. TEM micrographs of CoS_2 nanomaterials prepared in micellar AOT medium showing some degree of aggregation in the micellar network (A) 0.34 μM and (B) 1.89 μM

Fig. 10. TEM micrographs of CoS_2 prepared in SDS micellar medium showing well-separated spherical particles (A) 0.34 μM and (B) 1.89 μM

Fig. 11. SAED pattern of the CoS_2 nanoparticles prepared in micellar templates of (A) AOT and (B) SDS showing fair degree of crystallinity

Water and oil forms a heterogeneous biphasic solution, in general, due to differences in their polarity and also to their molecular structure. Surfactants, when added to such biphasic systems, due to their amphiphilic molecular structure, their hydrophilic head groups point to the aqueous phase and the apolar hydrophobic groups remain buried into the oil continuum. The interfacial tension (γ) is thus lowered and the work required to diffuse one phase into another decreases. The diffusion of one phase into another thus leading to the formation of emulsion or microemulsion phase. For systems with larger droplets of the dispersed phase as in emulsion, the visible light undergoes multiple reflection and the system appears turbid⁶³. If the droplets are far smaller, the surface area increases to such an extent that sufficient number of

Fig. 12. Transmission electron micrographs of the core-shell and composites of CdS and HgS (A and B) CdS-HgS at molar ratio (A) 5 : 1, (B) 1 : 5, (C and D) HgS/CdS at molar ratio (C) 5 : 1 and (D) 1 : 5, (E and F) CdS/HgS at molar ratio (E) 2 : 3 and (F) 3 : 2. All molar ratios correspond to CdS : HgS ratio

surfactant molecules can be accommodated at the interfacial zone leading to sufficient lowering of the interfacial tension and the solution appears transparent and macroscopically homogeneous. This macroscopically homogeneous (microscopically heterogeneous), thermodynamically stable phase is termed as microemulsion⁷⁷.

In most of the cases with ionic surfactant, the head-head ionic repulsion destabilizes the system. In such a case, a fourth component, the co-surfactant is required. They are generally lower alkanols and amines. Their accumulation at the interface can minimize the head-head repulsion at the interface considerably lower the interfacial tension and due to their smaller tail length compared to the surfactants can induce a tilt at the interface, which helps in forming smaller droplets of the dispersed phase (Fig. 6). In such microemulsions, the components with lesser proportion forms the dispersed phase and the major component forms the dispersion medium. The amphiphiles orient in such a fashion in such system that their hydrophilic head groups remain dipped in the aqueous phase and the lipophilic tail groups remain in the oil phase, in order to minimize the strain otherwise arising out of such an arrangement in the absence of the amphiphiles at the interface. The microemulsion systems

can be of two types : water-in-oil (w/o) and oil-in-water (o/w). A schematic representation of a w/o microemulsion has been shown in Fig. 13. Pileni and coworkers⁷⁸⁻⁸³ have much exploited the w/o microemulsion route for the preparation of nanomaterials.

Fig. 13. Schematic diagram of water-in-oil microemulsion : (A) rigidly bound water, (B) loosely bound water and (C) normal or bulk water.

In the microemulsion route, we have prepared the nanomaterials of lead sulfide⁸⁴, copper ferrocyanide⁸⁵ and lead chromate⁸⁶ in AOT/*n*-heptane/water water-in-oil microemulsion. In addition to the spectroscopic and microscopic studies, we have also reported the calorimetric studies of enthalpy of formation of the materials. The TX-100/*i*-propanol/cyclohexanone/water quaternary reverse microemulsion system was used to prepare nanomaterials of copper iodide, copper chromate and copper sulfide⁸⁷. In this case, the growth of the particles were monitored using light scattering technique. Synthesis of tungstic acid⁸⁸ nanomaterial was performed in the quaternary microemulsion of TX-100/*n*-heptane/water microemulsion medium. It was observed that there was a minima in the hydrodynamic radius, as observed from light scattering studies at surfactant to cosurfactant weight ratio 1 : 2 whereas it follows a gradual increase with the water pool size governed by the water to surfactant concentration ratio (ω). The enthalpy of formation of the nanomaterial also followed a linear relationship with reciprocal of ω . We have reported the preparation and characterization of PbS nanomaterial using the microemulsion route. Here we used the anionic surfactant AOT for its ease of formation of the microemulsion phase without the aid of any fourth component, the co-

surfactant, to simplify the environment. The variation of particle size on the water to surfactant mole ratio (ω) was thoroughly studied. Particle size was again monitored using both light scattering and electron microscopic technique. The DLS histogram of particle size distribution has been shown in Fig. 14. The discrepancy between the data obtained using the two techniques was elaborated. In addition, the effect of varied [PbS] at a fixed ω was also studied spectroscopically. The particles were also isolated after organically passivating them using thiophenol and dodecanethiol. The isolated powder was copper-brown

Fig. 14. Size distribution of PbS nanoparticles at $\omega = 5$ (A) and at $\omega = 25$ (B) obtained from DLS measurements.

in colour and fairly monodispersed. The TEM micrographs of the capped and uncapped particles under different drying conditions are given in Fig. 15.

In the microemulsion route, the water pool in w/o microemulsion is used as the microreactor. The reactants are taken in two separate solutions of a microemulsion. They are then mixed together. The randomness of the droplets lead to their coalescence, whereby the

Fig. 15. TEM pictures of PbS nanodispersion : (A) without capping, (B) dodecanethiol capped, (C) thiophenol capped and (D) thiophenol capped. The Electron Diffraction Patterns are presented in the insets.

coprecipitation reaction occurs and the products remain in the water pool of the w/o microemulsion. Thereafter, the droplets separate again to decrease strain and maintain the nanosize of the dispersion. Coalescence of the droplets is guided by the interdroplet potential⁸¹ that, in turn, depends on the dielectric constant of the dispersion medium (i.e. the oil) and on the number of droplets. Pileni has worked^{80,81} on the droplet size of w/o microemulsion and the rate of inter droplet collision dependence on dispersion medium.

Water-soluble precursors are used in microemulsion. This can affect the homogeneous regime in the phase diagram. AOT is useful in this respect as it can stabilize the microscopically inhomogeneous but macroscopically homogeneous microemulsion phase over a wide range of composition, and salts normally do not severely affect the range. So, the water to surfactant molar ratio (ω) can be varied over a wide range. Thus, by manipulating water – surfactant composition, constant size droplets of increased number and increased size droplets of decreasing number can be prepared. Because of amphiphilic nature of the surfactant, it mostly populates at the water-oil interface arranging its hydrophilic polar head facing the surface of the particle residing in the water core resulting passivation of the nanomaterial surface. Increasing ω is a way of increasing particle size; polydispersity in particle size simultaneously increases.

Pileni extensively used the cation exchange resin to exchange the Na^+ of AOT with different counterions and used these salts to prepare w/o microemulsion for the synthesis of nanoparticles⁸⁹. We have employed Na-AOT as the surfactant and the water-soluble salts of cationic precursors in microemulsion in our study^{84–88}.

The nanoparticle surface is often capped with organic thiols because of high electron-donating tendency of S and strong metal→S back-donation due to the presence of vacant d-orbital in S. This is known as the chemical surface passivation (Fig. 16). It helps in isolating the nanomaterials by way of destabilization of the microemulsion phase. Also, it passivates the broken surface bonds¹⁶ and hydrophobic barrier generated due to repulsion among the capped organic layer around the particles/clusters and resists coagulation even in the solid state. In many cases, significant increase in the photoluminescence efficiency of the nanomaterial is observed. If the surface passivation is incomplete, there can be surface localized states having energies within the nanocrystal band gap. During surface passivation (inorganically or organically), the surface atoms may be bonded to another

Fig. 16. Thiol capped nanoparticles. The hydrophobic repulsion between the hydrophobic barriers stabilizes the particles even in solid state : (A) alkyl thiol capped material, (B) thiophenol capped material.

material of a much larger band gap, eliminating all of the energy levels inside the gap. The ideal termination naturally removes the structural reconstructions, leaves no strain, and simply produces an atomically abrupt jump in the chemical potential for electrons or holes at the interface¹⁸. This potential confines the electrons or holes inside the clusters, which rationalize the application of “particle in a box” model over the confinement of the electron. In some cases, the capped material on drying by simple evaporation leads to the formation of fractal like structures. It has also been reported that, dithiols can act as spacer between two linear arrays or stacks of nanomaterials⁹⁰.

Glass matrix as template has been used as a route for the synthesis of nanoparticles. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), on acid hydrolysis produces silica. Thiourea is used as the sulfide precursor, which yields S^{2-} at elevated temperature ($\sim 650\text{--}700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). It also generates H_2S under controlled pH condition⁹¹. Thiourea and the cationic precursor are added to TEOS and the mixture is then acid hydrolysed to form the silica matrix. The mixture on prolonged heating for 2–3 days at $\sim 100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ produces a semi-rigid matrix in which thiourea and the cationic precursor are immobilized and the system is then heated at $\sim 650\text{--}700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for a week to augment the reaction⁹². The cationic precursor being previously immobilized, the product is also fixed in space and the particle coagulation is restricted. Semiconductor doped glasses^{93–96} consisting of small crystallites embedded in a glass matrix have been studied quite extensively as non-linear optical materials. Si doped glass may be a good example in this category.

Nanocrystal assemblies :

The capped nanoparticles formed in solution phase by a chemical process cannot normally form a lattice because of repulsive energy. On evaporation of the solvent,

the free volume available for the particles gets reduced with increase in viscosity until it freezes in the solid phase^{1,97,98}. During this growth process, the nanocrystals orient themselves so as to maximize their attractive potentials (both van der Waals and dipolar) with the surroundings and the neighboring nanocrystals to have a preferred orientation to form superlattices⁹⁹. Such lattices have liquid like structure in radial distribution function^{100,101} with random packing of spherical hard spheres of the nanocrystals interspersed by soft-shells comprising the capping materials. Engineering of the spacing between nanocrystallites is, therefore, possible by cap exchange process. For example, the R₃PO capping group can be easily replaced by pyridine. Evaporation of pyridine capped nano-dispersion leads to optically clear thin films, where pyridine is weakly bound to the nanoparticles. On gentle heating under vacuum, the pyridine capping desorbs quantitatively leading to an entirely inorganic superstructure called the superlattice. The colloidal crystals can also be prepared from aggregated nanocrystals in dispersed phase or, it can be formed from precipitation of the dispersion. The aggregate structure depends on two major factors, the rate of destabilization and the striking co-efficient of the particles during aggregation. In very rapid destabilization, the particles quickly add and stick to others, forming low-density fractal aggregates. On slower destabilization, the superlattice formed is a close packed, i.e. high density but amorphous aggregate.

Natural opal gemstones are in fact analogous supercrystals of round silica particles in the 0.1 to 0.5 micron diameter range^{102,103}. Fenske and coworkers¹⁰⁴ reported the synthesis and crystallization of Cu₁₄₆Se₇₃(PPh₃)₃₀, each of 2 × 4 nm tiny fragment of the layered semimetal Cu₂Se. Reports of nanocrystallite of semiconductors such as CdSe⁹⁹, AgS¹⁰⁵ are already there in literature. Superlattices of TOPO (tetraoctylphosphine oxide) capped CdSe through controlled crystallization from octanol mixture under reduced pressure have been reported⁹⁹. Peng *et al.*¹⁰⁶ have reported the dimers of TOPO capped CdSe by linking the nanoparticles with *N*-methyl-4-sulfanylbenzamide followed by size selective precipitation. They have also investigated the effects of mixing organically capped CdSe by linking the nanoparticles with the conjugated polymer poly[2-methoxy, 5-(2'-ethyl)hexyloxy-*p*-phenylvinylene]¹⁰⁷.

Survey on semiconductor nanomaterials :

Semiconductor nanomaterials are of foremost importance because of their size-tunable band-gap and precession in energy of the eigenstates. Bellow is the survey on

some II-VI semiconductor materials of foremost importance.

The cadmium chalconides have been considerably studied. Pileni⁷⁸ reported the preparation and control over size distribution of CdS nanoparticles by varying the water to surfactant molar ratio (ω) of AOT/water/*i*-octane, w/o microemulsion. The ring pattern of CdS nanoparticle aggregates^{82,83} (prepared in microemulsion) was reported from TEM measurements. Triangular CdS aggregates with structural simulation has been also reported⁷⁹. Dutta and Fendler¹⁰⁸ prepared CdS nanoparticles in self-reproducing reverse micelles. Other mentionable reports on CdS could be 1,6-hexanedithiol capped CdS nanoparticles reported in reverse micelle¹⁰⁹. Surface passivated by 2-(dimethylamino)ethanediol hydrochloride and 3-mercaptopropanoic acid stabilised CdS was also prepared in aqueous medium¹¹⁰. Phosphotungstic acid stabilized CdS nanoparticles prepared in aqueous medium¹¹¹, CdS prepared in silicious MCM-41 nanotubes¹¹², preparation of CdS nanoparticle in chicken egg membrane^{113,114}, its synthesis in double hydrophilic block co-polymers¹¹⁵, preparation in perfluorinated ionomer membrane (Nafion)¹¹⁶, dithiobiurea capped CdS nanoparticles in aqueous medium¹¹⁷, polarization dependent absorption spectrum and presence of two satellites on the low energy side of the main peak in the emission spectrum of prepared single CdS nanocrystal are also reported¹¹⁸.

The CdSe crystallites are called "living polymers" in the sense that the growth stops when the feedstock monomers are depleted, yet continues if the feedstock is replenished¹⁰⁸. The photophysics of CdSe nanoparticles have been studied much extensively especially by Bawendi and coworkers who have annealed diethyl cadmium and trimethylsilylselenide in TOP-TOPO solvent⁴⁴. Recently, Wang *et al.*¹¹⁹ reported the preparation of ZnSe, CdSe and HgSe using solution chemical procedure using Se powder and KBH₄. The particles were stabilized by EDTA. Norris and Bawendi¹²⁰ reported the assignment of the size-dependant optical spectrum in CdSe quantum dots. From intra-band energy relaxation study, Klimov *et al.*¹²¹ found that in CdSe dots capped with hole accepting molecules, the e-h coupling is strongly reduced after the hole is transferred to a capping group. The wide colour tunability of CdSe-ZnS quantum dot was reported by Lee *et al.*¹²². The solvatochromic shifts in the absorption spectrum of CdSe quantum dots and the consequent change in polarization energy of the quantum dots have been reported by Leathedral and Bawendi¹²³. A detail study of photoconductivity of CdSe quantum dot solids was pro-

vided by Leathredale *et al.*¹²⁴. Identification of band-edge emission of CdSe nanoparticles was studied with the aid of an externally applied magnetic field and hence the importance of exciton spin dynamics in recombination mechanism was found by Nirmal *et al.*¹²⁵. The first attempt toward the nanocrystal quantum dot laser, i.e. the optical gain and stimulated emission from the quantum dot has been studied by Klimov *et al.*¹²⁶.

Kurth *et al.*¹²⁷ reported the synthesis of CdTe nanoparticles in dimethyldioctylammonium bromide solution and the preparation and luminescence property of thiol-stabilized CdTe nanocrystals was reported by Kapitanov *et al.*¹²⁸. Brigham *et al.*¹²⁹ prepared CdTe nanoclusters by vapour-phase deposition of elemental Te in a Na⁺-zeolite followed by partial exchange of the zeolite with aqueous Cd(NO₃)₂ solution. The statistical study on fluorescence intermittency (blinking statistics) has been done in single crystal CdTe nanoparticles by Shimizu *et al.*¹³⁰.

Bulk ZnS is an important inorganic material for light emitting applications. Wageh *et al.*⁵⁷ reported a highly luminescent mercaptoacetic acid capped ZnS nanoparticles. Kovtyukhova *et al.*¹³¹ reported the synthesis of ZnS, Mn doped ZnS, ZnO and SiO₂ nanoparticles on silica surface using sol-gel reactions. The photophysical properties of ZnS nanoclusters passivated with 1-thioglycerol and mercaptoethanol was studied by Kumhojkar *et al.*⁵⁸. Thiophenol capped ZnS nanoparticles were also reported by Mahamuni *et al.*⁵⁹. The optical nonlinearity in capped ZnS nanoclusters has also been reported¹³³. Tanigaki *et al.*¹⁹² reported the preparation of ZnS, ZnSe and ZnTe by gas evaporation technique. Bhattacharjee^{134,135} reported the synthesis of Mn doped ZnS in SiO₂ matrix and Lu *et al.*¹³⁶ reported the ZnS/polythiourethane nanocomposites, while luminescent properties of ZnS nanomaterials linked with several organic chromophores and temperature dependent structural study of ZnS nanoparticles were done by Yang *et al.*¹³⁷ and Quardi *et al.*¹³⁸, respectively. *In situ* surfactant monolayer supported synthesis of ZnS nanoparticles was reported by Zhao and Fendler¹³⁹.

The predominantly ionic semiconductor material PbS has also been extensively studied. Yang *et al.*¹⁴⁰ recently reported the preparation of PbS nanoparticles in the lamellar liquid crystalline water compartment of Triton-X 100/C₁₀H₂₁OH/H₂O water/oil microemulsion system. Rosetti *et al.*¹⁴¹ used a wet-chemical process whereby methanol/acetone and methanol/ethanol mixtures were used as solvent. Wang *et al.*¹⁴² prepared PbS nanoparticles in

ethylene-15% methacrylic acid copolymer. The surface passivated PbS microcrystals capped with 4-hydroxythiophenol has been reported by Torimoto *et al.*⁵². Series of alkanethiol protected PbS nanoclusters and sonochemical synthesis of large-scale single-crystal PbS nanorods have been reported by Chen *et al.*¹⁴³ and Zhou *et al.*¹⁴⁴ and Ogawa *et al.*¹⁴⁵, respectively. Yang *et al.*¹⁴⁶ prepared dodecanethiol protected PbS nanocrystallites in the bicontinuous cubic phase of concentrated aqueous AOT solution and Jiang *et al.*²⁰⁶ have prepared monodispersed PbS nanoparticles on monolayer of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid on Au substrate. Flores-Acosta¹⁴⁸ reported an account of excitonic absorption of PbS nanoparticles synthesized in zeolite and Thielsch *et al.*¹⁴⁹ reported the PbS embedded SiO₂ thin film by co-evaporation technique. The morphology control of PbS nanoparticles grown in surfactant monolayer in pure and mixed state was investigated by Fendler and coworkers^{150,151}. They¹⁵² also reported the n-type or p-type rectification obtained from PbS nanoparticles depending on the method of preparation. Nenadovic *et al.*¹⁵³ studied the influence of surface properties on transient bleaching of small PbS colloids. Guerreiro *et al.*¹⁵⁴ reported the synthesis by thermal treatment of an oxide glass and used the PbS quantum doped glass to continuous wave passive mode lock in a Cr : forsterite laser. Recently, Wu *et al.*¹⁵⁵ have reported the preparation of ultrasmall uncapped PbS quantum dots by electroporation of vesicles technique.

In this context, the formation of nanoparticles of CdS and HgS in Langmuir-Blodgett films¹⁵⁶, synthesis of HgS in aqueous solution of amino acids¹⁵⁷, and sonochemical method of formation of PbS and HgS can be mentioned¹⁵⁸⁻¹⁶⁰.

Recently, the field of semiconductor nanomaterials are becoming rich by the formation of double decker or triple decker clusters because of robust surface passivation by inorganic materials to have enhanced emission power and manipulation of the band gap. Hasselbarth *et al.*¹⁶⁶ reported the synthesis of CdS/HgS colloids supported by sodium polyphosphate. They observed a strong red shift (from 500 nm to 950 nm) on coating HgS by CdS; for the composite particles of HgS on CdS, the fluorescence maxima was reported in between 550-700 nm. Reports on the formation of CdS/HgS/CdS triple decker quantum dots are also available in literature¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹¹. Tian *et al.*¹¹² made an extensive study on the core-shell and coupled composite of CdS-CdSe supported by sodium polyphosphate in aqueous solution. A photoassisted route to synthesize CdSe and CdSe/CdS core-shell type quantum dots was reported by Lin *et al.*¹¹³. Size-tunable

optical properties of solution grown PbS-FeS co-colloids was also reported¹¹⁴.

Considerable work has been done on CdSe/ZnS core/shell quantum dot composites. Dabbousi *et al.*¹¹⁵ prepared a series of highly luminescent ZnS coated CdSe nanocomposites. The photodarkening and electrodarkening of CdSe/ZnS core/shell composites were studied by Rodriguez-Viejo *et al.*²³⁷. Cumberland *et al.*²³⁸ have reported CdSe/ZnS nanomaterials prepared by organometallic route avoiding the annealing step, which provides larger control over particle size and shape. ZnS overcoated CdS has been prepared by Hsu and Lu¹¹⁸ through metal-organic chemical vapor deposition technique. They found a red-shift in the absorption spectrum on thermal annealing revealing a more complete and thicker CdS coverage on ZnS. Very recently, Mews and coworkers¹¹⁹ have reported highly luminescent multishell nanocrystals of the type CdSe-Core CdS/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}/ZnS.

The above description is a concise account of preparation and properties of nanomaterials and their futuristic implications. The rapid growth and diversification of the field of nanoscience make it ever challenging to the scientists and technologists.

Important uses of nanomaterials :

Because of size-tunable band-gap and precise energy of the energy states, semiconductor nanomaterials are very much useful in opto-electronic devices like optical switches and in preparing laser sources. They are employed in desk-jet printing technology and as memory storage devices. They find manifold uses as electronic diodes. Silica coated and ferrite doped nanoparticles are used in biomagnetic separation of cells, and magnetically guided drug delivery. Gold nanoparticles have been found to be prospective candidates in differentiating malignant tissues from benigns on the basis of shifts in their absorption spectra.

The microelectronics industry is searching for miniaturization, whereby the circuits, such as transistors, resistors, and capacitors are of reduced size. Minimization in size of the microprocessor, using these devices are of much prospect.

Nanomaterials, synthesized by the sol-gel method, results in formation of foam like structures, called "aerogel". They are three dimensional architectures of nanomaterials with trapped air in the interstices. These aerogels are porous and extremely lightweight; yet can withstand 100 times their weight. These aerogels can effectively been used as insulation in heating and cooling devices at reduced power cost. They are also used in

"smart" windows, which darkens at bright sun and lightens at deemed sun by themselves just similar to the sunglasses.

The resolution of a television, or a monitor, depends largely on the size of the pixel, which are made of "phosphors". The phosphors glows when a stream of electron impinges on it. A decrease in pixel size using the nanomaterials of ZnS, ZnSe, CdS, PbTe prepared by sol-gel techniques can improve the resolution of the monitor.

Since nanocrystalline carbides are much stronger, harder and wear resistance, they are currently used in cutting tools.

Conventional and rechargeable batteries are used in almost all applications that requires electric power like automobiles, laptops, electric vehicles, personal stereos, cellular and cordless phones, toys and watches. The life of the conventional and rechargeable batteries is low. Nanocrystalline materials synthesized by sol-gel techniques are candidates for separator plates in batteries because of their foam-like structure, which can hold considerably more energy than conventional ones. Moreover, nickel-metal hydride batteries made of nanocrystalline nickel and metal hydrides are envisioned to require far less frequent recharging and to last much longer because of their large grain-boundary area and enhanced physicochemical and mechanical properties.

The strength of a magnet is measured in terms of coercivity and saturation magnetization values. These values increase with a decrease in the grain size and an increase in the specific surface area of the grains. It has been shown that magnets made of nanocrystalline yttrium-samarium-cobalt grains possess very unusual magnetic properties due to their extremely large surface area. Typical applications of these high-power rare earth magnets include quieter submarines, automobile alternators, land-based power generators, motors for ships, ultra-sensitive analytical instruments, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in medical diagnostic.

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